

FORMULATION, DEVELOPMENT AND OPTIMIZATION OF NOVEL VESICLE SYSTEM CONTAINING THICOLCHICOSIDE BY DESIGN OF EXPERIMENT APPROACH

Ajay Kumar¹ Kaushelendra Mishra^{2*}, Richa Verma³, Dr. Mehta Parulben D⁴

¹Research Scholar- Lakshmi Narain College of Pharmacy, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh

²Professor- Lakshmi Narain College of Pharmacy, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh

³Associate Professor- Lakshmi Narain College of Pharmacy, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh

⁴Director- Lakshmi Narain College of Pharmacy, Kalchuri Nagar, Raisen Road, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh India-462021

Corresponding author : Kaushelendra Mishr

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to develop and optimize a novel vesicular drug delivery system glycosomes for the effective encapsulation and controlled release of Thiocolchicoside, a poorly water-soluble muscle relaxant. Pre formulation studies confirmed the physicochemical suitability of the drug for vesicular encapsulation, including optimal solubility in DMSO, stability at physiological pH, and an absorption maximum at 367.0 nm. A Box–Behnken Design (BBD) was employed to evaluate the influence of phospholipid, glycerol, and cholesterol concentrations on two critical parameters: particle size and entrapment efficiency. The optimized formulation achieved a glycosomes size of 365.4 nm, high entrapment efficiency of 94.06%, and a zeta potential of 31.5 mV, indicating physical stability. SEM analysis confirmed spherical morphology with no aggregation. The in vitro release study demonstrated sustained drug release up to 18 hours, fitting Higuchi and Korsmeyer–Peppas kinetic models, indicating a diffusion-controlled mechanism. The optimized glycosomal formulation remained stable over 3 months under both room and accelerated conditions. These findings suggest that glycosomes are a promising and stable delivery platform for enhancing the bioavailability and therapeutic efficacy of Thiocolchicoside.

Keywords: Glycosomes, Thiocolchicoside, Box–Behnken Design, Vesicular System, Entrapment Efficiency, Sustained Release, Diffusion-Controlled Release, Stability Study.

1. INTRODUCTION

DoE is a statistical approach used to optimize formulations by systematically varying independent variables and evaluating their impact on dependent variables (responses). A DoE technique like Box-Behnken or Central Composite Design can be used to create a set of formulations with varying combinations of the independent variables. Statistical analysis of the data allows for the identification of the optimal formulation with the desired characteristics (Myers *et al.*, 2016).

Glycosomes are vesicles composed of phospholipids, glycerol, and water. They are designed for topical or transdermal drug delivery, offering advantages like enhanced drug permeation through the skin due to the presence of glycerol, which increases vesicle

flexibility and hydration. Glycerol can also modify the lipid organization of the stratum corneum, further aiding drug penetration (**Kováčik et al., 2020**).

Thiocolchicoside a natural anti-inflammatory glycoside it is the semi-synthetic derivative of the colchicine. It originates from the flower seeds of *Superba Gloriosa*. It is a muscle relaxant with anti-inflammatory and analgesic effects (**Bhamburkar et al., 2022**). It has potent convulsant activity and should not be administered to individuals prone to seizures. It is used in the treatment of orthopedic, traumatic and rheumatologic disorders. It is indicated as an adjuvant drug in the treatment of painful muscle contractures and is indicated in acute spinal pathology (**Zhu et al., 2014**).

Thiocolchicoside acts on muscular contractures by activating the GABA inhibitory pathways because it has a selective and potent affinity for γ -aminobutyric acid A (GABA-A) receptors thereby behaving as a potent muscle relaxant. In human cortex the main inhibitory neurotransmitter is Gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) (**Eken et al., 2024**). GABAergic neurons are involved in the anesthetics, myorelaxation, and sedation and in the treatment of anxiolytic. GABA can also modulate heart rate and blood pressure. It acts as a muscle relaxant because it has an affinity for the inhibitory glycine receptors i.e. glycomimetic and GABA mimetic activity. Glycine is an inhibitory neurotransmitter and acts as an allosteric regulator of NMDA (N-methyl-D-aspartate) receptors. It regulates the movement, vision by processing the motor and sensory data (**Mizzi and Blundell 2025**).

The present study was aimed towards the quality by design assisted formulation and development and Optimization of novel vesicle system (Glycosomes) containing thiocolchicoside topical delivery by Design of experiment (DoE).

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Chemicals

Lead acetate, were obtained from Samuh Laxmi Chemicals (Bom) P. Ltd. Kezi Industries provided the Glacial Copper sulphate. Orient Micro Abrasives Limited provided the Hydrochloric acid while Panoli Intermediate supplied Conc. Ammonium sulphate was procured from Vinipul Inorganics India, a well-known provider of high-quality laboratory chemicals. Ferric chloride was supplied by Drashti Chemicals. All other solvents, Chemicals and reagents used were of analytical (AR) grade and purchased from Ams Fine Chemical, Pandora Industries, Suvchem, Manas Petro Chem and Vizag chemical.

2.2 Pre-formulation studies of Drug

2.2.1 Organoleptic Properties

Thiocolchicoside is a yellow to yellow-green crystalline powder with a characteristic appearance (**Asher, 2020**).

2.2.2 Solubility

Solubility plays a crucial role in pharmaceutical development, directly impacting a drug's absorption, bioavailability, and therapeutic effectiveness (**Jindal et al., 2024**).

2.2.3 pH Determination

The pH value of Thiocolchicoside was measured to assess its acid-base behavior, which is essential for predicting stability, solubility, and compatibility with excipients during formulation development. A digital pH meter was employed for the analysis (**Annapurna, 2018**).

2.2.4 Melting Point

Thiocolchicoside, the melting point was measured using the open capillary method in conjunction with a Thiele's tube apparatus (Joshi and Gupta, 2013).

2.2.5 Determination of Lambda max and calibration curve of Thiocolchicoside

- **Lambda (λ) max**

To determine the wavelength of maximum absorbance λ max for Thiocolchicoside, a standard stock solution was prepared by dissolving 1 mg of the drug in 1 mL of methanol. From this, a working solution with a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ was obtained through appropriate dilution using the same solvent. The UV-visible absorption spectrum of the working solution was recorded within the range of 200–400 nm using a Shimadzu 1700 double-beam UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The λ max was identified as the wavelength corresponding to the highest absorbance on the spectrum. This λ max value was then used for subsequent quantitative analysis. Additionally, a calibration curve was constructed by measuring the absorbance of solutions at varying concentrations to establish a linear relationship for accurate drug quantification in formulation studies (Kokilambigai and Lakshmi 2021).

- **Standard calibration curve**

A quantity of 100 mg of Thiocolchicoside was accurately weighed and transferred into a 100 mL volumetric flask. The drug was dissolved in methanol, and the volume was brought up to the mark with the same solvent to obtain a primary stock solution (1 mg/mL). From this stock, 1 mL was pipetted into a 10 mL volumetric flask and diluted with methanol to produce a working standard solution with a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. This working solution was subjected to UV spectrophotometric analysis using a Shimadzu 1700 double-beam spectrophotometer. The solution was scanned across the wavelength range of 200–400 nm to determine the maximum absorbance wavelength λ max of thiocolchicoside. This standard curve served as a reference for determining the concentration of thiocolchicoside in unknown samples during formulation and analysis (Aprile *et al.*, 2017).

2.2.6 Preparation of calibration curve

To establish a calibration curve for thiocolchicoside, a standard stock solution was first prepared by dissolving the drug in methanol. This stock was then serially diluted with the same solvent to produce a series of standard solutions with concentrations of 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90, and 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Each of these solutions was analyzed using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer at the previously determined λ max, using methanol as the blank. The resulting graph displayed a linear relationship, which was used to calculate the concentration of thiocolchicoside in unknown formulations or test samples with precision and accuracy (Ma'mun *et al.*, 2021).

2.2.7 Fourier transmission Infra-Red Spectroscopy

Fourier Transform Infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy was employed to analyze the pure drug and its physical mixture with excipients to identify possible interactions and confirm the presence of characteristic functional groups. Approximately 1 mg of thiocolchicoside (or drug-

excipient blend) was finely ground and mixed with 100 mg of spectroscopic-grade potassium bromide (KBr), which had been pre-dried under an infrared lamp to remove moisture. This disc was carefully placed in the sample holder of the FT-IR spectrophotometer, and the spectrum was recorded. The resulting spectra were analyzed for characteristic absorption peaks, which provided insights into the structural integrity of the drug and any potential interactions between the drug and formulation components (Nanda *et al.*, 2012)

2.3 Preparation of drug loaded Glycosomes formulation by thin film hydration process

The thin film hydration approach was employed for the preparation of Drug-loaded GMs. Cholesterol (2 to 5%), phospholipid (15 to 30 mg), and thiocolchicoside (0.1 %) were accurately measured and dissolved in chloroform with methanol. The resulting mixture was mechanically stirred at 40°C for one hour. Subsequently, the mixture was evaporated using a rotary evaporator under reduced pressure, leading to the formation of a clear lipid film on the rounded bottom of the flask. To hydrate the Drug-loaded-GMs, a glycerol-Phosphate buffer solution 6.8 was used, and the two phases were mechanically stirred at 40°C for one hour. The vesicles were then subjected to sonication for half cycle. To remove any excess un-entrapped drug, the resulting formulation was centrifuged at 1500 rpm for 10 min at 4 °C before being lyophilized for future use (Alhakamy *et al.*, 2021, Rani *et al.*, 2021).

Table 1: Composition of Glycosomes formulation

Formulation code	Thiocolchicoside (%)	Phospholipid (mg)	Glycerol (%)	Cholesterol %	Methanol (ml)	Chloroform (ml)	PBS 6.8 (ml)
GS 1	0.1	15	10	3.5	10.0	10.0	15.0
GS 2	0.1	30	20	5	10.0	10.0	15.0
GS 3	0.1	22.5	10	2	10.0	10.0	15.0
GS 4	0.1	22.5	30	2	10.0	10.0	15.0
GS 5	0.1	30	20	2	10.0	10.0	15.0
GS 6	0.1	15	20	5	10.0	10.0	15.0
GS 7	0.1	22.5	30	5	10.0	10.0	15.0
GS 8	0.1	30	10	3.5	10.0	10.0	15.0
GS 9	0.1	22.5	10	5	10.0	10.0	15.0
GS 10	0.1	15	20	2	10.0	10.0	15.0
GS 11	0.1	15	30	3.5	10.0	10.0	15.0
GS 12	0.1	30	30	3.5	10.0	10.0	15.0

2.4 Design of experiment

Using Design of Experiment (Version 12.0.1.0) software, the experiment was designed for the glycosome formulation. In this instance, the second-order polynomial model represented the quadratic response surfaces. Tables 2 display the variables that are independent and dependent that was chosen.

2.4.1 Independent and Dependent variables

Table 2: Independent and Dependent variables

Independent variables	Dependent variables
(X1) Polymer Phospholipid (mg)	(R1) Particle size (nm)
(X2) Surfactant Glycerol (mg)	(R2) EE (%)
(X3) Cholesterol	

2.4.2 Values of variables

Table 3: Values of variables

Factor	Name	Units	Type	Minimum	Maximum	Coded Low	Coded High	Mean	Std. Dev.
A	Phospholipid	mg	Numeric	15.00	30.00	-1 ↔ 15.00	+1 ↔ 30.00	22.50	6.40
B	Glycerol	%	Numeric	10.00	30.00	-1 ↔ 10.00	+1 ↔ 30.00	20.00	8.53
C	Cholesterol	%	Numeric	2.00	5.00	-1 ↔ 2.00	+1 ↔ 5.00	3.50	1.28

2.5 Evaluation parameter of Drug loaded Glycosome

2.5.1 Physical Appearance

The physical appearance of the drug-loaded glycosome formulation was visually inspected to assess its clarity, color, homogeneity, and phase separation (**Md et al., 2021**).

2.5.2 Particle Size

In this study, the average particle size and size distribution of the thiocolchicoside-loaded glycosomes were determined using a Malvern Zetasizer (Malvern Instruments, UK) (**Paradkar and Vaghela 2018**).

2.5.3 Zeta potential

The diluted samples were then assessed using a Malvern Zetasizer (Malvern Instruments). Zeta potential measurements were conducted to evaluate the surface charge and electrostatic stability of the thiocolchicoside-loaded glycosomes (**Anwer et al., 2025**).

2.5.4 Scanning Electron Microscopic (SEM):

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) was utilized to examine the surface morphology and structural characteristics of the thiocolchicoside-loaded glycosomes. SEM provides high-resolution images that allow for detailed visualization of particle shape, surface texture, and aggregation state, which are crucial for understanding the formulation's physical properties. For SEM analysis, a small volume of the glycosome dispersion was placed on a clean aluminium stub and allowed to dry under vacuum at room temperature.

2.5.5 Entrapment efficiency

The entrapment efficiency of thiocolchicoside in glycosomes was determined indirectly. The glycosome dispersion was centrifuged at 15,000 rpm for 30 minutes using a REMI Ultra Using a calibration curve, the concentration of free drug was measured, and the amount encapsulated was calculated by subtracting this from the total drug added. Entrapment efficiency (%) was then computed using the formula: (**Moolakkadath et al., 2020**).

Entrapment efficiency % = Total drug conc. - Supernatant drug conc. / total drug conc. × 100

2.6 In Vitro drug release

The in vitro drug release profile of thiocolchicoside-loaded glycosomes was evaluated using the dialysis bag diffusion technique. A known quantity of the glycosomal formulation was accurately placed into a dialysis membrane, which was sealed and immersed into a beaker containing 100 mL of phosphate buffer (pH 6.8). The system was maintained at 37 ± 2 °C on a magnetic stirrer at 100 rpm, simulating physiological conditions. At predetermined time intervals, 2 mL of the release medium was withdrawn and replaced immediately with an equal volume of fresh buffer to maintain sink conditions (**Paradkar and Vaghela, 2018**).

2.7 Stability Testing of Optimized Glycosome-Loaded Formulation of Thiocolchicoside

Stability is a critical component in pharmaceutical product development, defined as the capacity of a drug substance or formulation to retain its physical, chemical, therapeutic, and toxicological characteristics throughout its shelf life under specified storage conditions. Stability testing provides essential data on how the quality of a drug product changes over time when exposed to environmental factors such as temperature, humidity, and light. This information is crucial for determining suitable storage conditions, retest periods, and the product's shelf life. In the present study, stability testing was performed on the optimized batch of the glycosome-loaded formulation of thiocolchicoside, following the guidelines established by the International Conference on Harmonisation (ICH) for accelerated stability studies. The formulation was sealed in airtight containers and stored in a stability chamber under two controlled conditions:

- $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ with $60 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity (RH)
- $40 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ with $70 \pm 5\%$ RH

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Pre-formulation study

3.1.1 Organoleptic properties

Table 4: Organoleptic properties of Thiocolchicoside

Drug	Organoleptic properties	Observation
Thiocolchicoside	Color	Yellow to yellowish powder
	Odor	Odorless or faint characteristic odor
	Appearance	Fine crystalline or amorphous powder
	State Thiocolchicoside	Solid

3.1.2 Solubility study

Table 5: Solubility study of Thiocolchicoside

Drug	Solvents	Observation/Inference
Thiocolchicoside	Water	Slightly soluble
	Ethanol	Freely soluble
	Methanol	Freely soluble
	Chloroform	Sparingly soluble
	DMSO	Freely soluble

3.1.3 pH and melting point determination

Table 6: pH and melting point of Thiocolchicoside

Drugs	Observed (pH)	Observed (Melting Point)	Reference (Melting Point)
Thiocolchicoside	7.0	194°C	$190 - 198^\circ\text{C}$

3.1.4 Lambda max of Thiocolchicoside

Table 7: Lambda max

Drug	UV absorption maxima (Lambda max)
Thiocolchicoside	367.0 nm

3.1.5 Calibration curve of Thiocolchicoside

Graph 1: Calibration curve of Thiocolchicoside

3.1.6 Functional group identified by Infra-Red spectroscopy

Graph 2: FTIR study of Thiocolchicoside

Table 8: Interpretation of IR spectrum of Thiocolchicoside

Peak obtained	Reference peak	Functional group	Name of functional group
3415.69	3500- 3400	N-H stretching	primary amine
1625.64	1662-1626	C=Stretching	Alkane
1155.92	1170-1155	S=O Stretching	Sulfonamide
1071.58	1075-1020	C-O stretching	Alkyl aryl ether
1030.17	1070-1030	S=O stretching	sulfoxide

3.2 Optimization of formulation by design of expert (DOE) software

The formulation experiment involved a specific component mixture, resulting in the preparation of 12 distinct batches of glycosomes. Each batch was evaluated for the designated responses. Upon analyzing the data from 12 experimental runs, it was determined that a linear model provided the best fit for both dependent variables. To evaluate the model's statistical significance compared to alternative models, an Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was conducted. All responses were recorded across the 12 runs, and the tables illustrate the correlation between the independent and dependent variables.

3.2.1 Build information

Table 9: Build information of DOE software

File Version	12.0.1.0		
Study Type	Response Surface	Subtype	Randomized
Design Type	Box-Behnken	Runs	12
Design Model	Quadratic	Blocks	No Blocks

3.2.2 Independent and Dependent variables

Table 10: Variables showing for optimization process

Variables	Coding	Variables
Independent variables	A	(X1) Phospholipid
	B	(X2) Glycerol
	C	(X3) Cholesterol
Dependent variables	R1	Particle size (nm)
	R2	Entrapment efficiency (%)

3.2.3 Formulation trials as per Box–Behnken design

Table 11: Formulation trials

Formulation code	Thiocolicoside (%)	Phospholipid (mg)	Glycerol (%)	Cholesterol %	Methanol (ml)	Chloroform (ml)	PBS 6.8 (ml)	Particle size (nm)	Entrapment efficiency (%)
GS 1	0.1	15	10	3.5	10.0	10.0	15.0	408.11	93.63
GS 2	0.1	30	20	5	10.0	10.0	15.0	436.42	94.55
GS 3	0.1	22.5	10	2	10.0	10.0	15.0	463.17	92.46
GS 4	0.1	22.5	30	2	10.0	10.0	15.0	756.81	77.07
GS 5	0.1	30	20	2	10.0	10.0	15.0	230.44	95.21
GS 6	0.1	15	20	5	10.0	10.0	15.0	753.19	85.26
GS 7	0.1	22.5	30	5	10.0	10.0	15.0	533.78	80.11
GS 8	0.1	30	10	3.5	10.0	10.0	15.0	280.46	96.28
GS 9	0.1	22.5	10	5	10.0	10.0	15.0	401.21	93.18
GS 10	0.1	15	20	2	10.0	10.0	15.0	561.23	84.44
GS 11	0.1	15	30	3.5	10.0	10.0	15.0	647.75	85.23
GS 12	0.1	30	30	3.5	10.0	10.0	15.0	588.35	87.06

3.2.4 Limits of Variables (Constraints)

Table 12: Variables operating range for glycosome formulation

Name	Goal	Lower Limit	Upper Limit	Importance
A: Phospholipid	is in range	15	30	3
B: Glycerol	is in range	10	30	3
C: Cholesterol	is in range	2	5	3
Particle size	none	230.44	756.81	3
Entrapment efficiency	none	77.07	96.28	3

3.2.5 Fit Summary

Table 13: Response 1: Particle size

Source	Sequential p-value	Adjusted R ²	Predicted R ²	
Linear	0.0247	0.9877	0.9899	Suggested
2FI	0.9339	0.3313	-0.7509	
Quadratic	0.8871	-0.0291	-3.4905	Aliased

3.2.6 Effect of formulation variables on Particle size (ANOVA for Quadratic model)

- Response 1: Particle size

Table 14: Response 1: Particle size (ANOVA for Quadratic model)

Source	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	2.072E+05	69062.55	5.44	0.0247	significant
A-Phospholipid	87071.73	87071.73	6.86	0.0307	
B-Glycerol	1.185E+05	1.185E+05	9.34	0.0157	
C-Cholesterol	1594.71	1594.71	0.1256	0.7322	

Residual	1.015E+05	12693.52			
Cor Total	3.087E+05				

Final Equation in Terms of Coded Factors

Particle Size= +505.08 Intercept -104.33 Polymer (AX1) +121.72 Surfactant (BX2) +14.12 Cholesterol (CX3)

For certain amounts of each element, predictions regarding the reaction can be made using the equation expressed in terms of coded factors. By default, the components' high and low levels are denoted by the numbers +1 and -1, respectively. The coded equation is useful for identifying the relative impact of the factors by comparing the factor coefficients.

Graph 3: Graphical representation of Residuals vs run, Normal plot of Residuals and Cooks distance of glycerosome formulation on particle size

3.2.7 Predicted value and actual value of Particle Size and Entrapment efficiency

Table 15: Predicted value and actual value of all formulations

Formulations	Actual Value of Particle size	Predicted Value of Particle size	Actual Value of % entrapment efficiency	Predicted Value of % entrapment efficiency
GS 1	408.11	487.69	93.63	91.40
GS 2	436.42	414.87	94.55	92.26
GS 3	463.17	369.24	92.46	93.98
GS 4	756.81	612.68	77.07	82.46
GS 5	230.44	386.63	95.21	91.28
GS 6	753.19	623.52	85.26	86.13
GS 7	533.78	640.91	80.11	83.44
GS 8	280.46	279.03	96.28	97.53
GS 9	401.21	397.48	93.18	94.96
GS 10	561.23	595.28	84.44	85.15
GS 11	647.75	731.12	85.23	79.88
GS 12	588.35	522.47	87.06	86.01

Graph 4: Two-dimensional contour plots for the effect of polymer and surfactant concentration on particle size

Graph 5: Response surface plot showing combined effect of polymer and surfactant on particle size of glycosome

3.3 Effect of formulation variables on Entrapment efficiency

Table 16: Response 2: Entrapment efficiency (Fit Summary)

Source	Sequential p-value	Adjusted R ²	Predicted R ²	Suggested
Linear	0.0065	0.9805	0.9772	Suggested
2FI	0.9907	0.4990	-0.3118	
Quadratic	0.3109	0.6168	-0.6723	Aliased

3.3.1 ANOVA for Linear model

- **Response 2: EE (ANOVA Linear model)**

Table 17: Response 2: EE (ANOVA Linear model)

Source	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	significant
Model	342.62	114.21	8.81	0.0065	significant
A-Phospholipid	75.28	75.28	5.81	0.0425	
B-Glycerol	265.42	265.42	20.47	0.0019	
C-Cholesterol	1.92	1.92	0.1482	0.7103	
Residual	103.71	12.96			
Cor Total	446.33				

$$\text{Entrapment efficiency} = +88.71 + 3.07 AX1 - 5.76 BX2 + 0.4900CX3$$

For certain amounts of each element, predictions regarding the reaction can be made using the equation expressed in terms of coded factors. By default, the components' high and low levels are denoted by the numbers +1 and -1, respectively. By comparing the factor coefficients, the coded equation can be used to determine the relative importance of the elements.

Graph 6: Graphical representation of Residuals vs run, Normal plot of Residuals and Residuals vs predicted of glycosome formulation on Entrapment efficiency

Graph 7: Two-dimensional contour plots for the effect of polymer and surfactant concentration on % entrapment efficiency

Graph 8: Response surface plot showing combined effect of Polymer and surfactant on entrapment efficiency of glycosome formulation (Three dimensional)

- **Optimized formula of glycosome formulation**

Table 18: Optimized formula of glycosome formulation

Phospholipid	Glycerol	Cholesterol	Particle size (Predicted)	Entrapment efficiency (Predicted)	Desirability	
27.436	11.519	2.026	319.313	95.129	1.000	Selected
22.621	17.458	4.282	479.803	90.476	1.000	
19.397	28.640	3.477	653.174	82.454	1.000	

Table 19: Final Composition of optimized glycosome formulation as per Design of experiment approach

Formulation code	Thiocolchicoside (%)	Phospholipid (mg)	Glycerol (%)	Cholesterol (%)	Methanol (ml)	Chloroform (ml)	PBS 6.8 (ml)
GS	0.1	27.436	11.519	2.026	10.0	10.0	15.0

3.4 Characterization of optimized formulation

3.4.1 Physical appearance of drug loaded glycosome formulation

Table 20: organoleptic properties

Physical appearance	Observation
Color	Pale yellow to greenish-yellow
Clarity	Slightly opaque or translucent
Consistency	Gel-like or semi-solid
Odor	Mild, characteristic
Phase Separation	Absent (homogeneous appearance)

3.4.2 Particle Size and zeta potential

Table 21: Particle size of optimized formulation

Formulation	Particle size (Predicted value)	Particle size (Actual value)	Zeta potential
Glycosome	319.3 nm	365.4 nm	31.5 mV

3.4.4 Entrapment efficacy

Table 22: Entrapment efficacy

Formulations	Entrapment efficacy (Predicted value)	Entrapment efficacy (Actual value)
Glycosome	95.12 %	94.06 %

3.4.5 Scanning Electron Microscopic (SEM) Analysis

Figure 1: SEM

3.5 In Vitro Drug Release Study of Thiocolchicoside-Loaded Glycosomes

3.5.1 Drug release study of Glycosomes formulation

Table 23: Drug release study of Glycosomes formulation

Time (Hr)	cumulative % drug released	% drug remaining	Square root time	log Cumu % drug remaining	log time	log Cumu % drug released
0	0	100	0.000	2.000	0.000	0.000
2	18.26	81.74	1.414	1.912	0.301	1.262
4	33.5	66.5	2.000	1.823	0.602	1.525
6	48.22	51.78	2.449	1.714	0.778	1.683
8	59.74	40.26	2.828	1.605	0.903	1.776
10	70.27	29.73	3.162	1.473	1.000	1.847
12	79.08	20.92	3.464	1.321	1.079	1.898
14	88.33	11.67	3.742	1.067	1.146	1.946
18	96.62	3.38	4.243	0.529	1.255	1.985

Graph 13: Release study of all formulations

3.5.2 Kinetics Models of optimized formulation

3.6 Stability study

Table 24: Stability Study of optimized formulation (Glycosomes)

Time (Days)	25°C±2 °C and 60 ± 5% RH		40°C±2 °C and 70 ±5% RH	
	Particle size (nm)	Entrapment efficacy (%)	Particle size (nm)	Entrapment efficacy (%)
0	365.4 nm	94.06%	365.4 nm	94.06%
30	365.2 nm	94.05%	365.4 nm	94.05%
45	365.0 nm	94.01%	365.7 nm	94.03%
60	365.0 nm	93.94%	365.9 nm	94.02 %
90	365.1 nm	93.98%	365.7 nm	94.02%

4. CONCLUSION

This study successfully developed and optimized a novel glycosome-based delivery system for Thiocolchicoside using a statistically driven DoE approach. The optimized formulation demonstrated favorable physicochemical characteristics, high entrapment efficiency, nanoscale particle size, and controlled drug release behavior. The vesicular system enhanced the solubility and stability of Thiocolchicoside, making it a promising candidate for improved topical or transdermal delivery. Additionally, the application of Box–Behnken Design provided a robust framework for evaluating formulation variables with fewer experiments. Overall, this research confirms the potential of glycosomes as an effective and stable drug delivery system for poorly water-soluble drugs like Thiocolchicoside, warranting further in vivo evaluation and clinical translation.

5. REFERENCES

- Myers, R. H., Montgomery, D. C., & Anderson-Cook, C. M. (2016). *Response surface methodology: process and product optimization using designed experiments*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Kováčik, A., Kopečná, M., & Vávrová, K. (2020). Permeation enhancers in transdermal drug delivery: Benefits and limitations. *Expert opinion on drug delivery*, 17(2), 145-155.
- Bhamburkar, S., Khandare, S., Patharkar, S., & Thakare, S. (2022). Thiocolchicoside: an updated review.
- Zhu, H. L., Wan, J. B., Wang, Y. T., Li, B. C., Xiang, C., He, J., & Li, P. (2014). Medicinal compounds with antiepileptic/anticonvulsant activities. *Epilepsia*, 55(1), 3-16.
- Eken, R., Kesilmez, E., Secinti, K., Akkaya, Z., Secinti, İ., Turkoğlu, H., & Yüksel, Z. (2024). Effect of Thiocolchicoside on Midline Closure in Early Chicken Embryos. *Cyprus Journal of Medical Sciences*, 9(3).
- Mizzi, N., & Blundell, R. (2025). Glycine receptors: Structure, function, and therapeutic implications. *Molecular Aspects of Medicine*, 103, 101360.
- Asher, A. H. (2020). *On the Ion Conductivity through Energy-Dependent Translocon Complexes and the Interfacial Proton Pool at the Thylakoid Membrane in Pisum Sativum*. University of California, Davis.
- Jindal, K., Arora, S., & Goswami, M. (2024, February). Development of subcutaneous system for thiocolchicoside and evaluation for in-vitro permeability studies. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2986, No. 1). AIP Publishing.
- Annapurna, M. M. (2018). New derivative spectrophotometric methods for the determination of thiocolchicoside –A semisynthetic derivative of colchicoside. *International Journal of Green Pharmacy (IJGP)*, 12(01).
- Joshi, R. R., & Gupta, K. R. (2013). Solid-state characterization of thiocolchicoside. *International Journal of Advanced Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*, 4, 1441-1450.
- Kokilambigai, K. S., & Lakshmi, K. S. (2021). Utilization of green analytical chemistry principles for the simultaneous estimation of paracetamol, aceclofenac and thiocolchicoside by UV spectrophotometry. *Green Chemistry Letters and Reviews*, 14(1), 99-107.
- Aprile, S., Canavesi, R., Bianchi, M., Grosa, G., & Del Grosso, E. (2017). Development and validation of a stability-indicating HPLC-UV method for the determination of Thiocolchicoside and its degradation products. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis*, 132, 66-71.
- Ma'mun, A., Alamein, A. M., Elrahman, M. K. A., & El-Kawy, M. A. (2021). Three Stability Indicating Spectrophotometric and Spectrodensitometric Methods for the Determination of Thiocolchicoside in Presence of Its Degradant. *Analytical Chemistry*.
- Nanda, R. K., Patil, S. S., & Navathar, D. A. (2012). Chiotsan nanoparticles loaded with thiocolchicoside. *Der Pharma Chemica*, 4(4), 1619-1625.
- Md, S., Alhakamy, N. A., Aldawsari, H. M., Husain, M., Khan, N., Alfaleh, M. A., ... & Akhter, M. H. (2021). Plumbagin-loaded glycerosome gel as topical delivery system for skin cancer therapy. *Polymers*, 13(6), 923.

- Rani, D., Sharma, V., Manchanda, R., & Chaurasia, H. (2021). Formulation, design and optimization of glycosomes for topical delivery of minoxidil. *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology*, 14(5), 2367-2374.
- Md, S., Alhakamy, N. A., Aldawsari, H. M., Husain, M., Khan, N., Alfaleh, M. A., & Akhter, M. H. (2021). Plumbagin-loaded glycosome gel as topical delivery system for skin cancer therapy. *Polymers*, 13(6), 923.
- Paradkar, M., & Vaghela, S. (2018). Thiocolchicoside niosomal gel formulation for the pain management of rheumatoid arthritis through topical drug delivery. *Drug Delivery Letters*, 8(2), 159-168.
- Anwer, M. K., Alshdefat, R., Akhtar, J., & Aleemuddin, M. (2025). Punica granatum Loaded Glycosomes for Antibacterial Effect in Skin Infections: Preparation, Optimization, In Vitro and In Vivo Characterization. *BioNanoScience*, 15(2), 1-15.
- Moolakkadath, T., Aqil, M., Ahad, A., Imam, S. S., Praveen, A., Sultana, Y., & Mujeeb, M. (2020). Preparation and optimization of fisetin loaded glycerol based soft nanovesicles by Box-Behnken design. *International journal of pharmaceutics*, 578, 119125.
- Paradkar, M., & Vaghela, S. (2018). Thiocolchicoside niosomal gel formulation for the pain management of rheumatoid arthritis through topical drug delivery. *Drug Delivery Letters*, 8(2), 159-168.